

THE ROLE OF ADMINISTRATIVE OFFENSE CASES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CRIME PREVENTION BY INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

G'aniyev Elyor

Senior official of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

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Today, many reforms are being carried out in order to strengthen law and order and legality in our country, to ensure peace and tranquility of the population by ensuring public safety, forming a comprehensive system for preventing offenses and combating crime, establishing effective activities of internal affairs bodies from the lowest level to the republican level, and introducing modern methods of work. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196, modern information technologies are being introduced into the activities of crime prevention units, aimed at increasing their efficiency and reducing their overload. According to it, "The mahalla law enforcement center is the main sub-unit of ensuring public safety in the region, preventing crime and combating crime, and the task of ensuring public safety, systematic organization and coordination of work to prevent crime and combat crime by the mahalla law enforcement center is assigned to the prevention inspector"

As a result of the large-scale reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan, comprehensive measures are being implemented aimed at introducing modern information and communication technologies into the system of state administration bodies and all other sectors, integrating information systems of ministries and agencies, ensuring their continuous operation, information security, and creating convenience for our people through digitalization. Explaining the concept of "case management," this term refers to a type of activity related to ensuring document circulation in various departments and institutions (reproduction and storage of copies of stenograms and minutes of meetings, adopted decisions and orders; receipt and registration of correspondence, sending correspondence, etc.). The term "business administration" was translated from the Russian word "business production" and introduced into our language. However, as it turned out, in our history, those who carried out writing in palaces and large offices in general were called "munshi" (Arabic). Recall the following lines from the novel "The Scorpion from the Altar" by the renowned writer Abdulla Kodiri: "When Anvar reached the stage of the chancellery, the elders, mirzas, and munshis inside rose to

congratulate their new leader." Therefore, as an alternative to the term "business manager" translated from Russian, the word "munshiy" can be recommended as a root and synonym, as well as the word "munshaot," which was used in the language of our ancestors in the past

When analyzing the work carried out by internal affairs bodies in the field of crime prevention during 2022, in order to prevent neglect among minors, 100,065 children left unattended in public places were identified. Of these, 28,014 were placed in social and legal assistance centers, and 207 children left without parental care were appointed guardians and trustees. Based on the principle of "Safe Educational Institution," inspector psychologists conducted 135,374 preventive sessions with 89,098 children with difficult upbringing, visited their homes 133,208 times, and administered administrative measures to 77,752 parents who neglected their child's upbringing. Furthermore, in handling cases of administrative offenses, the internal affairs bodies are considering them based on Article 272 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, which ensures equality of citizens before the law and the body (official) reviewing the case, regardless of gender, social origin, personal and social status, race, nationality, language, religion, or beliefs.

In particular, in 2023, in accordance with the principle of equality of citizens, administrative offense cases were concluded for 14,475 persons out of 14,334 cases in Andijan region, 13,128 persons out of 9,457 cases in Bukhara region, 7,760 persons out of 6,527 cases in Jizzakh region, 18,459 persons out of 12,850 cases in Kashkadarya region, 7,167 persons out of 6,520 cases in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 16,825 persons out of 13,217 cases in Namangan region, 18,393 persons out of 13,791 cases in Samarkand region, 9,031 persons out of 7,214 cases in Syrdarya region, 13,809 persons out of 9,996 cases in Surkhandarya region, 27,029 persons out of 18,772 cases in Tashkent region, 24,720 persons out of 21,771 cases in Tashkent city, 22,593 persons out of 17,035 cases in Fergana region, and 10,922 persons out of 9,185 cases in Tashkent city. Based on the above, it can be concluded that today, as in any developed or developing country, our Republic's important path of development is founded on the principles of building a state with a solid legal foundation that embodies the highest level of civil society, based on strong legislation. When an administrative offense is committed by an offender residing in a different area within the administrative territory assigned to the preventive inspector, there are difficulties related to detaining this person and bringing them to court. Specifically, special rooms and technical equipment have not been allocated at

the mahalla law enforcement centers to detain offenders. To address these issues, it is advisable to establish special detention facilities in the mahalla law enforcement offices and equip them with the necessary technical means.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Маъмурий жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги кодекси. Электрон манба: <https://lex.uz/docs/97664>
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2023 йил 11 июлдаги “Экология ва жамоат тартибини сақлаш соҳаларидаги қонунчилик такомиллаштирилиши муносабати билан ўзбекистон республикасининг айрим қонун ҳужжатларига ўзгартиш ва қўшимчалар киритиш тўғрисида”ги ЎРҚ-854-сонли Қонуни. Электрон манба: <https://lex.uz/docs/6530788?ONDATE=13.10.2023%2000#6530981>
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2021 йил 8 июлдаги “Маъмурий ҳуқуқбузарликлар тўғрисидаги ишларни юритишнинг электрон тизимини жорий этиш бўйича қўшимча чоратадбирлар ҳақида”ги қарори. Электрон манба: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5500086>
4. Раҳмонов Р., Акбаров Ж. Профилактика инспекторлари фаолиятида ахборот-таҳлил ва режалаштиришнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари //Наука и технология в современном мире. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 341-344